

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<https://arseam.com/content/volume1issue1-may-2014>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

CORROSION INHIBITION STUDIES OF ALUMINIUM METAL IN 1 N SODIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTION BY SUBSTITUTED TRIAZOLES DERIVATIVES

Ramlath K T

Assistant Professor (Chemistry)

KAHM Unity Women's College, Manjeri, Malappuram District .Kerala. Pin 676122, India

ABSTRACT

Aluminum is an important metal used in industry since it is an excellent electrical and thermal conductor with low density, high ductility, and good corrosion resistance. However, under most natural conditions unless special precautions are followed, metals undergo corrosion. The subject of metallic corrosion has gained considerable importance during last few decades because of the increasing awareness of the enormous losses caused by corrosion damage. It has been reported that the protective oxide film of aluminium can readily undergo corrosion reactions in chloride environments. For this reason, the corrosion mechanism of aluminum in chloride solutions has been investigated in a number of studies.

1,2,4-triazole and their derivatives are known for its characteristic of corrosion inhibition. They are nontoxic and inexpensive and are heterocyclic compounds containing different donor atoms. These compounds can be adsorbed on the metal surface through lone pairs of

electrons on nitrogen or sulfur atoms and also through pi electrons present in these molecules.

This study focuses on the corrosion inhibitory action of ATD (4-amino- 4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3, 5-dimethanol) and SAMT (3-amino-5-methylthio-1H-1,2,4-triazole) on aluminium metal in 1N NaCl by the classical weight loss method, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and Potentio-dynamic polarization methods. The results shows that both ATD and SAMT show good inhibitive efficiencies for aluminium in 1N NaCl and the percentage inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration. Polarization studies reveal that both ATD and SAMT act as mixed type inhibitors and Polarization studies shows that ATD has better inhibitive efficiency than SAMT towards aluminium at lower inhibitor concentrations. At 200 ppm, this tendency changes; ATD and SAMT possess almost the same inhibitory actions. SEM images further confirm all the above observations.

KEY WORDS: Corrosion Inhibition, Triazoles (ATD & SAMT), LPR & LPC, Nyquist plots, Electro chemical impedance spectrum(EIS).

*Corresponding author: * Ramlath K T

Reference this paper as: Ramlath K T (2014). "Corrosion inhibition studies of Aluminium metal in 1 N sodium chloride solution by substituted triazoles derivatives," *International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research*, Vol.1, Issue 1, May-2014, pp 38-64

INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is degradation of a material, usually metal, or its properties due to interactions with their environments. Even though it is inevitable, substantial barriers (corrosion control methods) can be used to slow its progress toward the equilibrium state. Thus it is the rate of the approach to equilibrium that is often of interest. This rate is controlled not only by the nature of the metal surface, but also by the nature of the environment as well as the evolution of both. Thus with most metals, this means that under most natural conditions unless special precautions are followed, metals undergo corrosion. The subject of metallic corrosion has gained considerable importance during last few decades because of the increasing awareness of the enormous losses caused by corrosion damage. Corrosion costs of automobiles-fuel systems, radiators, exhaust systems and bodies-are in the billions.

Aluminum is an important metal in industry owing to its excellent characteristics including its good electrical and thermal conductivities, low density, high ductility, and good corrosion resistance. It is widely used as a material for automobiles, aviation, household appliances, containers and electronic devices [1-2]. The corrosion resistance of aluminum arises from its ability to form a natural oxide film on its surface in a wide variety of media [2-4]. It has been reported that the oxide film can readily undergo corrosion reactions in chloride

environments. For this reason, the corrosion mechanism of aluminum in chloride solutions has been investigated in a number of studies [1-5].

1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives are incorporated into a wide variety of therapeutically important compounds possessing a broad spectrum of biological activities and many other applications including corrosion inhibition of metals[6,7]. These hetero cycle compounds are particularly interesting for pharmaceutical applications because they are more likely to be water soluble than standard aromatic systems, and are stable under biological conditions. These compounds can be adsorbed on the metal surface through lone pairs of electrons on nitrogen or sulfur atoms and also through pi electrons present in these molecules [8]. The crystal structure, quantum-chemical calculations, spectroscopic properties and thermal decomposition products of 1, 2, 4 triazole derivatives have been studied by many authors [9-13].

Azole derivatives have been reported to inhibit the corrosion of different metals such as copper, iron, etc. [14-17]. Many substituted triazole compounds have been studied in considerable details as effective corrosion inhibitors [18-23]. Among the various nitrogenous compounds studied as inhibitors, triazoles have been considered as environmentally acceptable chemicals [24]. They are nontoxic and inexpensive and are heterocyclic compounds containing different donor atoms.

Objectives of the study

By following up the pathways of corrosion inhibition studies the present study, is aimed at shed particular focus on the experimental frame work to conduct corrosion inhibitory action of ATD (4-amino- 4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3, 5-dimethanol)

and SAMT (3-amino-5-methylthio-1H-1,2,4-triazole) on aluminium metal in 1N NaCl as a primary study as a foundation for further development of the studies of corrosion inhibition characteristics and materials

Corrosion and Passivation

Corrosion is degradation of a material, usually metal, or its properties due to interactions with their environments [25]. Even though it is inevitable, substantial barriers (corrosion control methods) can be used to slow its progress toward the equilibrium state. Thus it is the rate of the approach to equilibrium that is often of interest. This rate is controlled not only by the nature of the metal surface, but also by the nature of the environment as well as the evolution of both. Thus with most metals, this means that under most natural conditions unless special precautions are followed, metals undergo corrosion.

It is convenient to classify corrosion by the forms in which it manifests itself, the basis for this classification being the appearance of the corroded metal. The forms of corrosion are Unique ,but interrelated. Some of the are Uniform attack, Galavanic corrosion, cervice corrosion, Pitting corrosion, Inter-granular corrosion , exfoliation corrosion, Selective leaching , Erosion corrosion, and Passivation

Passivation refers to the spontaneous formation of an ultra-thin film of corrosion products known as passive film, on the metal surface that act as a barrier to further oxidation. The chemical composition and microstructure of a passive film are different from the underlying metal. Typical passive film thickness on aluminum, stainless steels and alloys is within 10 nanometers. The passive film is different from oxide layer or scale that is frequently formed at high

temperatures and is in the micrometer thickness range. The passive film has the unique property of self-healing while the oxide layer or oxide scale does not. For example, when scratch the surface of aluminium, the damaged passive film will be healed spontaneously by the instantaneous oxidation of aluminium from the underlying metal. Passivation in natural environments such as air, water and soil at moderate pH is seen in such materials as, aluminium, stainless steel, titanium and silicon.

Passivation is primarily determined by metallurgical and environmental factors. The effect of pH is recorded using Pourbaix diagrams, Some conditions that also inhibit passivation include: High pH for aluminium and zinc, low pH or the presence of chloride ions for stainless steel, high temperature for titanium (in which case the oxide dissolves into the metal, rather than the electrolyte) and fluoride ions for silicon

Corrosion in passivated materials

Passivation is extremely useful in mitigating corrosion damage, however even a high-quality alloy will corrode if its ability to form a passivating film is hindered. Proper selection of the right grade of material for the specific environment is important for the long-lasting performance of this group of materials, whether chemical or mechanical.

Pourbaix diagram

Pourbaix or E-pH diagrams depict the thermodynamically stable form of an element as a function of potential and pH [26]. Pourbaix diagrams allow determining the corrosion behavior of a metal in water solutions i.e. the direction of electro-chemical processes and the equilibrium state of the metal at a certain electrode potential in a water solution at a certain

value of pH. Normally the Pourbaix diagrams are built for the water solutions with the concentrations of metal ions $10^{-6}M$ and at the temperature 298K.

A simplified Pourbaix diagram indicates regions of "Immunity", "Corrosion" and "Passivity", instead of the stable species. Immunity means that the metal is not attacked, while corrosion shows that

general attack will occur. Passivation occurs when the metal forms a stable coating of an oxide or other salt on its surface, the best example being the relative stability of aluminium because of the alumina layer formed on its surface when exposed to air.

Pourbaix diagram for Aluminium

3 Regions: corrosion, passivation, immunity

In regions where:

- Al³⁺ is stable -corrosion is possible
- Aluminium oxide is stable - resistance or passivity
- Al is stable -thermodynamically immune to corrosion
- If pH < 4 -Al³⁺ stable
- If pH > 8.3 -Al₂O₂⁻ stable
- If 4 < pH < 8.3 -Al₂O₃ stable and thus protects the metal if the potential is sufficiently low- Aluminium itself is immune to corrosion

Electrochemical aspects of corrosion

Corrosion is an electrochemical process [27,28].Corrosion usually occurs through the operation of a coupled electrochemical reaction. In order for

electrochemical reactions to occur, four components must be present and active. These components are the anode, cathode, electron path, and electrolyte. Anode is the area where metals loses electrons and goes through environment from metal surface as

per the voltage gradients affects it. Cathode is the site where electrons consumed. For each electron that is produced at an anodic site, an electron must be consumed at a cathodic site. In order to flow electrons from the anodic sites to cathodic sites, the electrons migrate through a metallic path. This migration occurs due to a voltage difference between the anodic and cathodic reactions. In some cases, the electron path is the corroding metal itself, in other cases, the electron path is through an external electrical path.

Electrolytes are solutions that can conduct electrical currents through the movement of charged chemical constituents called ions. Positive and negative ions are present in equal amounts. Positive ions tend to migrate away from anodic areas and toward cathodic areas. Negative ions tend to migrate away from cathodic areas and towards anodic areas. Electrochemical corrosion involves two half-cell reactions; an oxidation reaction at the anode and a reduction reaction at the cathode.

Anodic reactions

When metal atoms are exposed to an environment containing water molecules they can give up electrons, becoming themselves positively charged ions provided an electrical circuit can be completed. This effect can be concentrated locally to form a pit or, sometimes, a crack, or it can extend across a wide area to produce general wastage

Cathodic reactions

A reduction reaction that is common in acids is hydrogen evolution,

Or Oxygen reduction

In neutral or alkaline media

As hydrogen forms, it could inhibit further corrosion by forming a very thin gaseous film at the surface of the metal. This "polarizing" film can be effective in reducing water to metal contact and thus in reducing corrosion. Yet it is clear that anything which breaks down this barrier film tends to increase the rate of corrosion. Dissolved oxygen in the water will react with the hydrogen, converting it to water, and destroying the film.

Corrosion protection by inhibition

Corrosion inhibitors are organic or inorganic chemical substances which, when added at low concentrations, are capable of preventing or controlling corrosion in 80–90% in most cases [29]. A corrosion inhibitor may be defined as chemical substance that can reduce the corrosion rate with the present of in small concentration without changing the concentration of corroding agent in a corrosion system. Corrosion inhibitor reduces the rate of corrosion with increase the polarization behavior of anode and cathode. Apart from that, lower the movement of ion to absorb to metal surface and finally increase the electrical resistance on metal surface [30].

The efficiency by which the corrosion process is reduced usually depends on the inhibitor concentration as well as characteristic system parameters, such as the solution pH, the concentration of aggressive species in the solution, the nature and the state of the metal surface, and the hydrodynamic conditions. Practical criteria for the selection of corrosion inhibitors from the great variety of inorganic and organic substances with

inhibiting properties are not only their inhibition efficiency but also safety of use, economic constraints, and compatibility with other chemicals in the system and environmental concerns. The use of highly efficient inorganic inhibitors such as chromates and zinc salts, are used less due to their toxicity and are nowadays largely replaced by organic inhibitors.

Organic inhibitors are often weak acids/bases, de-/protonating in aggressive media. Regardless which form of the molecules (neutral or charged) is responsible for the inhibitory action, it has been generally accepted that the inhibitor species should firstly diffuse towards the metal/solution interface, then the rate of degradation will be diminished by subsequent adsorption of the species, blocking the active-sites of the metal surface [31].

Organic compounds, mainly containing oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atoms and having multiple bonds, are recognized as effective inhibitors of the corrosion of many metals and alloys. In different media, for a given metal, the efficiency of the inhibitor depends on the stability of the formed complex and the inhibitor molecule should have centers, which are capable of forming bonds with the metal surface via an electron transfer. Generally, a strong co-ordination bond causes higher inhibition efficiency, the inhibition increases in the sequence $O < N < S < P$ [32].

Usually, inhibition results from the formation of an adsorption layer or protective film, which influences the electrochemical reactions involved in the corrosion process [33]. In other cases, the inhibitor promotes the passivation of the metal or modifies the solution chemistry, for example, by scavenging aggressive species.

Inhibition by adsorption

Many organic inhibitors work by adsorption mechanism. Inhibitors are usually specifically adsorbed species that adsorb directly on the metal surface in a process involving chemisorptions, in which the adsorbate chemically interacts with the surface, and physisorption, caused by much weaker van der Waals interactions. The dependence of the adsorbate surface coverage θ on the concentration of the adsorbate species in the solution C is described by the adsorption isotherm. Different types of adsorption isotherms are

$$\text{Temkin isotherm } \exp \int (\theta) = K_{\text{ads}} C \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Langmuir isotherm } \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = K_{\text{ads}} C \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Frumkin isotherm } \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \exp - 2 \int (\theta) = K_{\text{ads}} C \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Freundlich isotherm } \theta = K_{\text{ads}} C$$

The general tendency of the adsorption energy to increase with the functional group in the order $O < N < S$ can be associated with the corresponding increase in polarizability. Since bare metals can be classified as soft acids as explained by HSAB principle [34]. Generally, the inhibition efficiency increase upon replacement of a hydrogen atom by electron-donating substituent. In addition, strongly polar substituent increases the dipole moment of the molecule resulting in a stronger adsorption.

Types of inhibitors

The overall corrosion rate of a freely corroding metal is determined by the anodic

and cathodic partial reactions, both of which can be affected by the inhibitor. It is therefore common to distinguish anodic, cathodic and mixed inhibitors, dependent on the type of electrochemical reactions that are inhibited.

Synergistic effects

In practical formulations, it is common to use several different inhibitor species; frequently a combination of anodic and cathodic inhibitors. The simultaneous use of two or more different inhibitor species often results in a more efficient inhibition than the sum of the individual effects of the inhibitors.

Methods for studying corrosion

The weight loss studies

The Weight Loss technique is the best known and simplest of all corrosion monitoring techniques. The method involves exposing a specimen of material (the coupon) to a process environment for a given duration, then removing the specimen for analysis. The basic measurement which is determined from corrosion coupons is weight loss; the weight loss taking place over the period of exposure being expressed as corrosion rate. The technique is extremely versatile, since weight loss coupons can be fabricated from any commercially available alloy.

The disadvantage of the coupon technique is that, such procedures may require hundreds of hours or years to detect corrosion with any degree of precision and accuracy. But it can provide a useful correlation with other techniques such as EIS and LPR measurements. Also, using appropriate geometric designs, a wide variety of corrosion may be studied.

Measures of corrosion rate

Corrosion rates can be given in a number of different units using different measures of material loss. In Gravimetric method the corrosion rate is measured by immersing a sample into a corrosive environment for a period of time and measuring the weight loss during that time. The weight loss must be normalized by the sample area in order to determine a corrosion rate, so one set of proper units for corrosion rate is weight loss per unit area per unit time; for instance, $\text{mgcm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. It is very common to divide this measure of weight loss corrosion rate by the density of the corroding material to get a corrosion rate in units of thickness lost per unit time; for instance, mils per year (mpy) or mm per year

$$\text{Corrosion rate} = \frac{534W}{DAT} \text{ (mpy)} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Or Corrosion rate} = \frac{87.6W}{DAT} \text{ (mmy)} \quad (9)$$

where:

W = weight loss in milligrams

D = metal density in g/cm^3

A = area of sample in cm^2

T = time of exposure of the metal sample in hours

Overview of Electrochemical theory

When a metal is immersed in a given solution, electrochemical reactions characteristic of the specific metal/solution interface result in an electrochemical potential, referred as 'the open circuit potential' (OCP) or 'corrosion potential', E_{corr} . The rate of oxidation and reduction reactions that give rise to E_{corr} are

expressed in terms of their electron flow per unit time, or current(i). For a system at E_{corr} the oxidation reaction occurs at a rate equal to the reduction reaction. Thus

$$I_{\text{ox}} = I_{\text{red}}$$

The value of either the anodic or cathodic current at E_{corr} is called the corrosion current, I_{corr} . If we could measure I_{corr} , we could use it to calculate the corrosion rate of the metal. Unfortunately, I_{corr} cannot be measured directly. However, it can be estimated using electrochemical techniques.

It is possible to impose potentials other than E_{corr} by polarizing the system away from E_{corr} , then either the oxidation reaction or the reduction reaction can be accelerated, and the current associated with the enhanced reaction will increase. By polarizing in a systematic manner and measuring the resulting total currents it is possible to extrapolate the values of I_{ox} or

Test cell

Figure I, represents the test cell used in a common electrochemical corrosion measurement. The test cell includes the metal specimen (commonly called the working electrode) and the solution in which the specimen is to be tested. The saturated calomel electrode (SCE) is a commonly used reference electrode. The location of the reference electrode is critical in cells in which large ohmic potential drops exist. In these cases, a Luggin capillary should be used to bring the sensing location of the reference electrode close to the working electrode surface and minimize the ohmic potential drop. The tip of the capillary should be no closer to the working electrode surface than

$$I_{\text{total}} = I_{\text{ox}} + I_{\text{red}} = 0$$

i.e., if one were to measure the current flowing through the specimen at E_{corr} , only the total current (zero) would be obtained.

I_{red} at E_{corr} . This extrapolated current is referred to as the 'corrosion current' (I_{corr}), since at E_{corr} , $I_{\text{ox}} = I_{\text{red}}$.

The relationship between current and potential at an electrode/electrolyte interface can be probed by both controlling the potential and measuring the current, or by controlling the current and measuring the potential. In order to investigate the relationship over a range of values, the controlled parameter is either stepped or scanned. The most common approach for determining the current/potential relationship is potentiodynamic scanning. The potential is scanned at a fixed rate between two set values and the current is measured at periodic interval a distance equal to twice the capillary diameter to prevent shielding effects. If the inner diameter of the lugging capillary gets too small, the resistance in the electrometer circuit can lead to oscillations in the potentiostat control circuit. Counter electrodes should be made from an inert material such as Pt or graphite, and should have enough area to prevent current limitations. In resistive electrolytes, the counter electrode should be as parallel as possible to the working electrode. Non uniform current distribution can lead to spurious results. For perfectly uniform current distribution, the working electrode should comprise one complete wall of the cell and the counter electrode should comprise the complete opposite wall.

Fig.I Model of a Test cell

Tafel extrapolation method

The mixed potential theory provides the basis for the determination of corrosion rate by Tafel extrapolation. A Tafel plot is

performed on a metal specimen by polarizing it about 250 mV anodically (+ve) and cathodically (-ve) from the E_{corr} . The resulting current is plotted on a logarithmic scale as shown in figure II.

Fig.II Potentiodynamic polarization curve

At E_{corr} , since $I_{ox} = I_{red}$, the current is at a minimum. The curved portion of the plot is due to enhancements of I_{red} or I_{ox} . At larger polarization values, the plot becomes linear. Extrapolation of these linear region

yields with slopes, known as Tafel constants β_{anodic} and $\beta_{cathodic}$, expressed in volts per decade of current. The linear portion meets at E_{corr} and at which I_{corr} can

be determined. From this, the corrosion rate can be determined.

$$CR = \frac{0.13I_{corr}(EW)}{AD} \quad (10)$$

where:

CR in milli inches per year

EW equivalent weight in g/eqt

Linear polarization (polarization resistance) method

The corrosion can be determined from the polarization resistance using the Stern–Geary equation, if the Tafel slopes are known:

$$I_{corr} = \frac{\beta_a \beta_c}{(\beta_a + \beta_c) 2.303 R_p} \quad (11)$$

The Stern–Geary equation is the basis for the linear polarization method in which the polarization resistance is determined typically by scanning the potential from a value slightly below the corrosion potential to one slightly above the corrosion potential. It is an extremely easy technique that has been put to considerable use in corrosion monitoring. The linear polarization technique is considered to be “nondestructive” relative to potential scanning over a wide range because the electrode is barely disturbed from the open circuit condition.

Fig .III Linear polarisation graph

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopic method

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a convenient and effective method of assessing the properties and performance of organic-coated metal systems. The AC impedance of an electrochemical cell can be determined by

applying a sine wave of potential (V) of a certain frequency (ω) and measuring the corresponding current (I) flowing across the cell. The ratio of potential and current is the impedance of the cell (Z) at the chosen frequency, according to Ohm’s law:

$$Z = \frac{V}{I} = \frac{V_0 \sin \omega t}{I_0 \sin(\omega t - \Psi)} \quad (12)$$

A spectrum can be obtained by varying the frequency of the applied signal, in which case the technique is called EIS.

Since the impedance is the ratio of two sine waves, it is a complex number that can be represented by an amplitude and a phase shift or as the sum of real and imaginary components,

$$Z(\omega) = Z'(\omega) + jZ''(\omega) \quad (13)$$

The electro chemical system represented by a simple corrosion reaction can be viewed as an electrical circuit (figure IV). The circuit elements are R_Ω , R_p and C_{DL} represent the uncompensated resistance (Resistance from the reference to the working electrode), the polarization resistance (resistance to electrochemical oxidation) and the Capacitance very close to the metal surface at the double layer.

Fig.IV. Circuit describing the behavior of a simple electrochemical interface.

The Figure V. shows the impedance spectrum presented in the format of a Bode plot. Both the log of the impedance magnitude and the phase angle are plotted as a function of the log of the frequency of the excitation signal in this format. It is very close to that of a perfect RC circuit.

Modern EIS analysis software allows fitting of the data to the behavior expected for a given equivalent circuit, such as the RC circuit shown in Fig.IV. Such fitting provides best values for all of the circuit components.

Fig V. Bode plots of EIS

Another common plot for impedance data in corrosion is the complex plane plot or Nyquist plot (figure VI) in which the imaginary component is plotted as a function of the real component at each

frequency. A perfect RC circuit such as is given in Fig. IV will form a semicircle in the complex plane, which intercepts the real axis twice.

Fig VI. Nyquist plot of EIS

Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is a microscope that uses electrons rather than light to form an image. SEM uses a focused beam of high-energy electrons to generate a variety of signals at the surface of solid specimens. The signals that derive from electron-sample interactions reveal information about the sample including external morphology (texture), chemical composition, and crystalline structure and orientation of materials making up the sample. There are many advantages in using the SEM instead of a light microscope. The SEM has a large depth of field, which allows a large amount of the sample to be in focus at one time. The SEM also produces images of high resolution, which means that closely spaced features can be examined at a high magnification. Preparation of the samples is relatively easy since most SEMs only require the sample to be conductive. The combination of higher magnification, larger depth of focus, greater resolution, and ease of sample observation makes the SEM one of the most heavily used instruments in research areas today.

In most applications, data are collected over a selected area of the surface of the sample, and a 2-dimensional image is generated that displays spatial variations in these properties. Areas ranging from approximately 1 cm to 5 microns in width can be imaged in a scanning mode using conventional SEM techniques. The SEM is also capable of performing analyses of selected point locations on the sample; this approach is especially useful in qualitatively or semi-quantitatively determining chemical compositions, crystalline structure, and crystal orientations.

Review of literature

Aluminum is an important metal in industry owing to its excellent characteristics including its good electrical and thermal conductivities, low density, high ductility, and good corrosion resistance. It is widely used as a material for automobiles, aviation, household appliances, containers and electronic devices [1-2].

The corrosion resistance of aluminum arises from its ability to form a natural oxide film on its surface in a wide variety of media [2-4]. The protective oxide films formed on the aluminum surface have a dual nature. These films consist of an adherent, compact, and stable inner oxide film covered with a porous, less stable outer layer, which is more susceptible to corrosion [35-37].

Passivation and activation can occur depending on the potential, the pH and the Cl⁻ concentration [38-39].

Al oxide solubility increases in acidic and alkaline medium, above and below the pH 4–9 range [40] which explain the importance of studying the role of pH as shown by Lampease et al [41].

It has been reported that the oxide film can readily undergo corrosion reactions in chloride environments. For this reason, the corrosion mechanism of aluminum in chloride solutions has been investigated in a number of studies [1-5].

Mazhar et al. [42] studied the electrochemical behavior of Al in chloride containing solutions using EIS at OCP in both acidic and neutral media. The authors demonstrated that the rate of the oxide film dissolution in the chloride-containing solutions is found to be markedly lower than that in other halide media, especially in fluoride solutions. Complex plane analysis of the oxide film formed on Al indicates that the corrosion resistance is

very high in neutral chloride solutions in comparison with acid solutions containing the same amount of chloride ions. The corrosion rate for the Al samples increases with increasing halide ion concentration and temperature [43].

The electrochemical behavior of aluminum and some of its alloys was investigated [44] in buffer solution of different pH. The inhibition of corrosion of these materials using inorganic passivators like sulphates, molybdates was discussed showing that inhibition efficiency is independent on the concentration of the passivating anion in the solution. The corrosion and passivation behavior of aluminum in alkaline solution in pH range from 2-11 has attracted the attention of many investigators [45-49]. Results indicated that increasing pH changing the cathodic reaction and increasing Cl^- ion concentration decreasing the cathodic reaction rate. On the other hand, the anodic reaction rate increased with increase in Cl^- concentration. The open circuit corrosion potential and the pitting potential shifted in the active (negative) direction with increasing pH and Cl^- ion concentration.

It is generally believed that the dissolution of aluminum oxide films, which leads to the corrosion of aluminum, results from the adsorption of chloride ions that react with aluminum cations in the oxide lattice, leading to the formation of a soluble aluminum hydroxychloride salt. This salt goes into solution allowing the films to dissolve, leaving the bare aluminum metal [50-51]. According to Hunkeler et al. [52] and Sato [53], a salt barrier of AlCl_3 is formed within the pits on their formation and converted to soluble AlCl_4^- , which diffuses into the bulk solution.

The protection of aluminum and its oxide films from the corrosive chloride

attack has been studied by many investigators using either inorganic oxidants including chromate [54-56], molybdate [55-57], and tungstate [55,58], organic compounds having polar groups, such as oxygen, sulfur, and nitrogen [1-2,59-61], and heterocyclic compounds containing functional groups and conjugated double bonds [62] as corrosion inhibitors.

Bronzoi *et al* studied that localized corrosion can be prevented by the action of adsorption inhibitors which prevent the adsorption of aggressive anions or by the formation of a more resistant oxide film on the metal surface [63]. Pitting type corrosion of aluminum alloys is reduced in the presence of most investigated inhibitors. The adsorption of most inhibitors is also found to obey Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. It was found that lower concentration of inhibitors inhibited efficiently than higher concentration for aluminum alloys [64]. Kharafi et al. observed that a series of inhibitors like molybdate and dichromate were found effective in passivating the aluminum metal or alloy surface [65]. But, now a days as these inhibitors are toxic for environment, it is encouraged to avoid the use of such inhibitors.

Nitrites are well- defined oxidizing agents. They are effective as corrosion inhibitor for aluminum due to powerful oxidizing properties. This reveals that oxide layer on the aluminum surface plays an important role on its corrosion in aggressive media [66].

The effect of nitrite and chromate inhibitor ions in varying concentrations on the corrosion of Al in near neutral chloride solution has been studied by Brett et al. [58] using measurements of the open circuit potential (OCP) and its variation with time, cyclic voltammetry, potential

step chronoamperometry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements. The results show that nitrite and chromate ions are both reasonably successful inhibitors. Al-Kharafi and Badawy [65] studied the influence of molybdate, sulphate, and dichromate inhibitor ions on the corrosion of Al and Al 6061 and Al-Cu alloys in chloride free basic solutions using EIS and polarization techniques, complemented with XPS studies. The results showed that $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ is more effective than MoO_4^{2-} or SO_4^{2-} in passivating Al and Al alloys and the inhibition properties of the anion dependent essentially on its concentration in the corrosion medium.

Organic compounds, mainly containing oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atoms and having multiple bonds, are recognized as effective inhibitors of the corrosion of many metals and alloys. In different media, for a given metal, the efficiency of the inhibitor depends on the stability of the formed complex and the inhibitor molecule should have centers, which are capable of forming bonds with the metal surface via an electron transfer. Generally, a strong co-ordination bond causes higher inhibition efficiency, the inhibition efficiency increases in the sequence $\text{O} < \text{N} < \text{S} < \text{P}$ [8].

It has been reported [67] that the inhibitor molecules are bonded to the metal surface by chemisorption, physisorption, or complexation with the polar groups acting as the reactive centers in the molecules. In general, the adsorption of an inhibitor on a metal surface depends on a few factors [1-2], such as the nature and surface charge of the metal, the adsorption mode, the inhibitor's chemical structure, and the type of the electrolyte.

The effect of 1, 5-naphthalenediol [1] and 1, 4-naphthoquinone [2] on Al

corrosion in 0.5 M NaCl has been reported. Yamaguchi and Yamamoto [68] also investigated the adsorption of poly (1, 5-naphthalenediol) on Al surface. In all these studies, the organic compounds have proven strong ability to be adsorbed than to form a complex with Al surface by the formation of the Al-O bond, which lead to the inhibition of Al corrosion.

1,2,4-triazoles and their derivatives are incorporated into a wide variety of therapeutically important compounds possessing a broad spectrum of biological activities and many other applications including corrosion inhibition of metals[6,7]. For example, triazoles are used in the manufacture of dyes and inks, corrosion inhibitors, and polymers. Additionally, triazole-containing molecules have been shown to have anti-allergenic[69], anti-bacterial and anti-HIV[70] activities, and are under study as drugs for the treatment of osteoarthritis[71]and obesity.[72]These hetero cycle compounds are more likely water soluble than standard aromatic systems, and are stable under biological conditions that is ideal for pharmaceutical use.

Azole derivatives have been reported to inhibit the corrosion of different metals such as copper, iron, etc. [14-17]. Many substituted triazole compounds have been recently studied in considerable details as effective corrosion inhibitors for steel in acidic media [18-22]. Among the various nitrogenous compounds studied as inhibitors, triazoles have been considered as environmentally acceptable chemicals [24]. They are nontoxic and inexpensive and are heterocyclic compounds containing different donor atoms. These compounds can be adsorbed on the metal surface through lone pairs of electrons on nitrogen or sulfur atoms and also through pi electrons present in these molecules [18].

The effect of 3-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AMTA) [23] on the inhibition of Al corrosion in both Arabian Gulf seawater and 3.5% sodium chloride solutions using different electrochemical techniques has been investigated. The inhibition of Al corrosion by AMTA molecules is achieved by their adsorption then formation of a complex with the aluminum oxide preventing the formation of aluminum chlorides, $AlCl_3$, or chloride complexes, $AlCl_4^-$ or even soluble oxychloride complexes, $Al(OH)_2Cl_2^-$, which lead to Al corrosion. AMTA as an inhibitor works by adsorption onto aluminum preventing its corrosion by preventing the formation of soluble chloride and oxychloride complexes on its surface.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Inhibitor

The inhibitor molecule 4-amino-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3,5-dimethanol (ATD) was synthesized by the condensation of glycolic acid with hydrazine hydrate. Hydrazine monohydrate (E. Merck) (3.75 g, 0.75 mol) was added drop wise at 0°C to 70% aqueous glycolic acid (E. Merck) (54.3 g, 0.50 mol). The resulting solution was heated at 120°C for 6 h. Then the reflux condenser was replaced with a downward condenser and reaction mixture was heated at 160°C for a further 18 hr allowing excess hydrazine hydrate and water to distil off. The yellowish crystalline solid formed after cooling was recrystallised from water to give analytically pure ATD [73]

ATD

The inhibitor molecule, 3-amino-5-methylthio-1H-1,2,4-triazole (SAMT) was purchased (Aldrich, 98%) and used without further purification. It has the structure given in figure below.

SAMT

Metal chosen

The working electrode was of 100% pure aluminium as determined by EDX spectra (figure.14). The metal specimens used in electro chemical studies are cut into $4.8 \times 1.9 \text{ cm}^2$ coupons, but only 1 cm^2 area was exposed during each measurements. Before measurements the samples were polished using different grades of emery paper followed by washing with Ethanol and Acetone. Metal specimens were cleaned according to ASTM standard G-1-72 procedure [74-77].

Medium

The medium for the study was made from reagent grade NaCl (E. Merck) and doubly distilled water. All tests were performed in aerated medium at room temperature and atmospheric pressure.

Electrochemical methods of studying corrosion

Electrochemical tests were carried out in a conventional three-electrode polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA, room temperature)/Borosilicate glass (high temperature) cell with platinum (1 cm^2 surface area) as auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the

reference electrode. The working electrode first immersed in the test solution for establishing a steady state open circuit potential (OCP) and then the electrochemical measurements were carried out with a computer controlled Gill AC electrochemical workstation (ACM, U.K, model no: 1475). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out with amplitude of 10 mV (RMS) AC sine wave in a frequency range of 10 kHz to 1 Hz. The potentiodynamic polarization curves were obtained in the potential range of -250 mV to +250 mV with a sweep rate of 16 mV/s. All electrochemical measurements were made after 1hr immersion in corrosive media in the absence and presence of inhibitors and the reasonably good reproducibility is achieved through repetition.

2.7 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphologies of the samples in the absence and presence of inhibitor was carried out using a digital Scanning Electron Microscope model SU6600 (Serial No: HI-2102-0003) with an accelerating voltage of 20.0 kV, at a scan speed-Slow5 and calibration scan speed of 25. Samples were attached on the top of an aluminium stopper by means of carbon conductive adhesive tape. All micrographs of the specimens were taken at the magnification of 500 xs. These samples underwent the same pre-treatment as used in electrochemical experiments before recording the SEM image.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Potentiodynamic polarization studies

Tafel polarization curves for aluminium in unstirred 1N NaCl solution in the absence and presence of various concentrations of ATD and SAMT at 298K are presented in fig. 7 and 8.

Electrochemical potentiokinetic parameters like corrosion potential (E_{corr}), cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes (β_c and β_a) and corrosion current density (I_{corr}) obtained from Tafel extrapolation of the polarization curve at 298K were given in Table 11 and 12. The corrosion inhibition efficiency was calculated using the relation:

$$\%IE = 1 - \frac{I_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}^0} \quad (21)$$

Where I_{corr}^0 and I_{corr} are uninhibited and inhibited corrosion current density respectively. The changes in the values of the anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes (β_a & β_c) suggest that both ATD and SAMT act as mixed type inhibitors. The linear polarization resistance (LPR) obtained from linear polarization curves (another form of Tafel plots, graphs not given) are also shown in Table 11 and 12 and that also represents good inhibition efficiency for the inhibitors.

The cathodic reaction for aluminum in aerated near neutral pH solutions has been reported to be the oxygen reduction as follows;

The adsorbed hydroxide species further reduced to be in the solution accordingly;

The curve shows steep slope in the anodic region, proves the formation of a passive film on the surface of aluminium. This film is formed by the anodic reaction on two steps as follows [50];

Then this aluminium hydroxide, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, transforms to the aluminium oxide, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$,

The breakdown of the passive film took place due to the occurrence of pitting corrosion under the influence of the negative applied potential and presence of aggressive species, chloride ions in the medium [1-2]. This was indicated by the abrupt increase in the current values at less negative potential, and can be explained by these reactions;

There are some opinions regarding the mechanism of pitting corrosion of Al in chloride containing solutions [50-53]. One claims that a salt barrier of AlCl_3 is formed within the pits on their formation to form AlCl_4^- as shown in Eq. which diffuses into the bulk of the solution allowing the pitting corrosion to occur. Another view suggests the aggressiveness of the chloride ions is ascribed to their adsorption and their reaction with Al (III) in the oxide lattice, which leads to the formation of oxychloride complexes, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2^-$

The formation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2^-$ as a soluble complex decreases the chemical inertness of the natural oxide film and consequently enhances the anodic dissolution of the Al metal.

The presence of inhibitor in the test solutions shifts the E_{corr} to more positive potential values. Also, the values of I_{corr} , decrease, while the RP values increase. The

positive shift in E_{corr} values in the presence of inhibitor indicates that inhibitor molecules adsorb on the surface and prevent the $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2^-$, (see Eq.), from being formed on the oxide film and thus decrease the aggressiveness of Cl^- as well as protect the surface from being pitted. This suggests that the inhibitor inhibits the corrosion of Al in NaCl solutions and its efficiency as a corrosion inhibitor increases with the increase of its content in the solution.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

In order to understand the adsorption and inhibition mechanism of ATD and SAMT on aluminium surface, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements were performed to the aluminium /electrolyte solution interface. The Nyquist plots for the uninhibited 1N NaCl solution and solution containing different inhibitor concentrations at various temperatures are given in Fig.9 and 10. The Nyquist plots display a capacitive loop at high frequencies (may be due to charge transfer of the corrosion process) and a straight line at low frequencies (may be due to diffusion of soluble reactant or product species). It is evident from the Fig. that the impedance loops measured are depressed semi-circles with their centers below the real axis. This “dispersing effect” is mainly due to the roughness and other in-homogeneities of the electrode surface [95-99]. So one constant phase element (Q) is substituted for the capacitive element in the equation to get a more accurate fit. The impedance of a constant phase element is described by the expression:

$$Z_Q = Y_0^{-1} (j\omega)^{-n} \quad (29)$$

Where Y_0 is a proportional factor, n has the meaning of a phase shift. For $n = 0$,

Q represents a resistance, for $n = 1$, a capacitance, for $n = 0.5$, a Warburg element and for $n = -1$ an inductance. According to Hsu and Mansfeld [100], the values of the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) can be obtained from the equation:

$$C_{dl} = Y_0(\omega_m'')^{n-1}$$

Where ω_m'' is the frequency at which the imaginary part of the impedance has a maximum.

The diameter of the semicircle is noticed to increase in the presence of inhibitor and up on the increase of its concentration as depicted in Fig.9 and 10. Charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) were given in Table 13 and 14. It is observed that the values of the polarization resistance increase with inhibitor concentration. In the case of impedance studies, %IE is calculated with the equation:

$$\%IE = 1 - \frac{R_{ct}^0}{R_{ct}} \tag{31}$$

Where R_{ct}^0 and R_{ct} are the values of the charge transfer resistance observed in the absence and presence of inhibitor. The inhibition efficiencies calculated from EIS studies, show the same trend of polarization measurements. The small difference in the inhibition efficiency of these two methods may be attributed to the different surface status of the electrode in these two measurements. EIS measurements were performed at the rest

potential, while in polarization measurements the electrode surface was polarized due to high over potential, non-uniform current distributions resulted from cell geometry, solution conductivity, counter and reference electrode placement etc., and will lead to the difference between the electrode area (36) actually undergoing polarization and the total area [78].

Scanning electron microscopy(SEM)

Surface examination using SEM was carried out to study the effect of inhibitors on the surface morphology of aluminium metal. Figure 13(a) shows SEM image of a polished aluminium sample. Figure 13 (b) shows SEM image of aluminium surface after immersion in 1N NaCl solution with no additives for 24 hr. This micrograph reveals that the surface was strongly damaged in the absence of inhibitor. Figures 13(c) and (d) show SEM images of the surface of aluminium immersed for 24 h in 1N NaCl solution containing 200 ppm of the inhibitor molecules respectively. The faceting observed in figure 13(b) was gone and the surface was free from pits and it was smooth. It can be concluded that the rate of corrosion is less in the presence of inhibitors. These observations also support the results of electrochemical studies and quantum chemical calculations pertaining to these inhibitors.

TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1 Electrochemical polarization parameter and corresponding inhibition efficiency for the corrosion of aluminium with various concentration of ATD in 1N NaCl.

Inhibitor conc. (ppm)	-E _{corr} (mV)	L.P.R (Ωcm ²)	β _a (mv/dec)	β _c (mV/dec)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	Corr. Rate (mm/yr)	%IE
Blank	683	17.38	75	730	0.0973	8.932	-
50	753	23.76	39	454	0.0290	2.658	70.24
100	794	34.75	51	347	0.0249	2.287	74.40
150	744	27.32	27	113	0.0181	1.662	81.39
200	739	33.05	27	103	0.0172	1.432	83.97

Table 2 Electrochemical polarization parameter and corresponding inhibition efficiency for the corrosion of aluminium with various concentration of SAMT in 1N NaCl.

Inhibitor conc. (ppm)	-E _{corr} (mV)	L.P.R (Ωcm ²)	β _a (Mv/dec)	β _c (mV/dec)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	Corr. Rate (mm/yr)	%IE
Blank	683	17.38	75	730	0.0973	8.932	-
50	737	18.54	33	409	0.0650	5.831	34.72
100	753	19.13	34	517	0.0601	5.172	42.10
150	760	20.56	30	450	0.0523	4.806	46.19
200	728	20.69	40	244	0.0144	1.321	85.22

Table 3 AC Impedance parameter for the corrosion of aluminium with various concentrations of ATD in 1N NaCl .

Inhibitor conc. (ppm)	R _{ct} (Ω cm ²)	C _{dl} (μF/cm ²)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	C.R (mm/yr)	N	IE (%)
Blank	2950	2.771	0.0963	8.843	0.89	-
50	10260	7.940	0.0277	2.540	0.93	71.25
100	14950	7.875	0.0190	1.745	0.85	80.27
150	16170	7.649	0.0176	1.613	0.88	81.76
200	15380	7.305	0.0174	1.510	0.90	80.82

Table 4 AC Impedance parameter for the corrosion of aluminium with various concentrations of SAMT in 1N NaCl .

Inhibitor conc. (ppm)	R _{ct} (Ω cm ²)	C _{dl} (μF/cm ²)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	C.R (mm/yr)	N	IE (%)
Blank	2950	2.771	0.0963	8.843	0.89	-
50	5710	10.80	0.0618	5.568	0.84	48.34
100	5913	7.875	0.0516	5.201	0.92	50.11
150	6041	5.805	0.0470	4.318	0.82	51.17
200	26930	4.229	0.0195	2.68	0.88	89.05

Figure 1 EDX spectra for aluminium metal specimen

Figure 2 Linear polarization curves (Tafel) for Aluminium in 1N NaCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of ATD at 298K

Figure 3 Linear polarization curves (Tafel) for Aluminium in 1N NaCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of SAMT at 298K

Figure-4 Nyquist plots of Aluminium in 1N NaCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of ATD at 298K.

Figure-5 Nyquist plots of Aluminium in 1N NaCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of SAMT at 298K.

Figure 6. SEM images of (a) aluminium metal.

(b) In 1N NaCl without inhibitor.

(c) In the presense of 200 ppm of ATD after 24 hour

(d) In the presense of 200 ppm of SAMT after 24 hours.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The inhibitor molecules ATD and SAMT show good inhibitive efficiency for aluminium in 1N NaCl.
- 2) The percentage inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration.
- 3) Polarization studies reveal that both ATD and SAMT act as mixed type inhibitors.
- 4) Polarization studies shows that ATD has better inhibitive efficiency than SAMT towards aluminium at lower inhibitor concentrations. At 200 ppm, this tendency changes; ATD and SAMT possess almost the same inhibitory actions.
- 5) SEM images further confirm all the above observations.

REFERANCES

[1.] E. M. Sherif, S.-M. Park, *Electrochim. Acta*, 51 (2006) 1313.

[2]. E. M. Sherif, S.-M. Park, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 152 (2005) B205.

[3]. W. R. Osório, N. Cheung, L. C. Peixoto, A. Garcia, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 4 (2009) 820.

[4]. W. Diggle, T. C. Downie, C. Goulding, *Electrochim. Acta*, 15 (1970) 1079.

[5]. Fang Wang, Yabin Wang, Yanni Li, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 6 (2011) 793.

[6]. Suma A R, Padmalatha Nayak J, Shetty A N *J. Metal. Mater. Sci.* 47, 51 (2005)

[7]. Bektas, H. Karaali, N. Sahin, D. Demirbas, A. Karaoglu, *S A Molecules*. 15, 2427 (2010)

[8]. Poornima, T. Nayak, J. Shetty A N. *J. Appl. Electro Chem.* 41, 223, (2011)

[9]. V. Krishnakumar, R.J. Xavier, *Spectrochim. Acta A* 60, 709 (2004).

[10] V. Krishnakumar, G. Keresztury, T. Sundius, R.J. Xavier, *Spectrochim. Acta A* 61, 261 (2005).

[11] S. Guhathakurta, K. Min, *J. Polym. Sci. B: Polym. Phys.* 47 22, 2178 (2009).

[12] S. Subashchandrabose, A.R. Krishnan, H. Saleem, V. Thanikachalam, G. Manikandan, Y. Erdogu, *J. Mol. Struct.* 981, 59 (2010).

- [13] J. Luo, J. Hu, W. Saak, R. Beckhaus, G. Wittstock, I.F.J. Vankelecom, *J. Mater. Chem.* 21–28 , 10426(2011).
- [14]. I. Yamaguchi, T. Yamamoto, *React. Funct. Polymers* 61 , 43(2004).
- [15] E. M. Sherif, S.-M. Park, *J. Electrochim. Acta*, 51, 4665 (2006).
- [16]E. M. Sherif, A. A Almajid, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 40 ,1555(2010).
- [17] K. Babić-Samardžija, C. Lupu, N. Hackerman, A. R. Barron, A. Lutge, *Langmuir*, 21 , 12187(2005).
- [18]. L. Wang, *Corros. Sci.* 48 ,608(2006).
- [19] M.A. Quraishi, H.K. Sharma, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 78 ,18(2003).
- [20] D. Gopi, K.M. Govindaraju, V. Collins, A. Prakash, L. Kavitha, *Appl. Electrochem.*375, 269 (2009)
- [21] H.H. Hassan, E. Abdelghani, M.A. Amin, *Electrochim. Acta* 52, 6359 (2007).
- [22] A. lalitha, S. Ramesh, S. Rajeswari, *Electrochim. Acta* ,51, 47 (2005).
- [23]. El-Sayed M. Sherif, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 6 , 1479(2011)
- [24]. S. Ramesh, S. Rajeswari, *Electrochim. Acta* 49,811 (2004).
- [25]. Pierre R.Roberge, Corrosion Engineering, Principles and Practice ,Mc Graw Hill, New York(2008)
- [26]. Pourbaix, M., Atlas of electrochemical equilibria in aqueous solutions. 2d English ed., Houston, Tex.: National Association of Corrosion Engineers,(1974)
- [27] Mars G.Fontana, Corrosion Enginnering,3rd edn.,Tata Mc Graw Hill(2005)
- [28] E.Mcafferty,Introduction to corrossionscience,springer,Alexandria,USA,(2010)
- [29]. Gonza, C. A.; Francisco J. R; Genesca´-Llongueras, *Electrochimica Acta*. Vol 54, (December 2008), pp.86-90. ISSN. 0013-4686
- [30] Pierre, R. R. (2000). Handbook of Corrosion Engineering. McGraw-Hill, ISBN. 0070765162, New Jersey, USA
- [31] M. Lashkari, M. Arshadi, *Chem. Phys.* 299 (2004) 131.
- [32]. Musa et al. 2009). *Corrosion Science*. Vol. 51, (October 2009),pp. 2393–2399, ISSN. 0010-938X.
- [33]. W. J. Lorenz, F. Mansfeld in *Corrosion Inhibition*(Ed.: R. H. Hausler), International Corrosion Conference Series, National Association of Corrosion Engineers, Houston, Tex.,1988, pp. 7–13.
- [34] R. G. Pearson, *J. Chem. Educ.* 1968, 45, 581.
- [35]. G. A. Capauano, W. G. Davenport, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 118 (1971) 1688.
- [36] I. B. Obot, N. O. Obi-Egbedi, S. A. Umoren, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 4 (2009) 863.
- [37] C. M. A. Brett, I. A. R. Gomes, J. P. S. Martins, *Corros. Sci.*, 36 (1994) 915.
- [38]. M.Stella and Micheli, *Corros. Sci*, 18,605(1978).
- [39] T.H.Nguyen and R.T.Foley, *J.electrochem. Soc.*, 127(6) ,(1989).
- [40] Pourbaix, M., 1966. Atlas of electrochemica. Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions. Pergamon press, New York
- [41].Lampease , and P. Koutsokos , *Corr. Sc.*, 36, No.6 , 1011 (1994)
- [42]. A.A. Mazhar, W.A. Badawy, M.M. Abou-Romia, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 29 (1986) 335.
- [43] Sayed S. Abdel Rehim, Hamdi H. Hassan, Mohammed A. Amin, *Applied Surface Science* 187 (2002) 279–290
- [44] W.A.Badawy, F.M.Al Kharafi and A.S.El-Azab, *Current Topics in electrochemistry* 5,143(1997).
- [45] T.Hurlen and A.T.Haug, *Electrochim.Acta*,29,1133.
- [46] M.R.Tabrizi and S.B.Lyon, G.E.Thompson and J.M.Ferguson, *Corros. Sci.*, 32(7), 733(1991).
- [47] T.Kiyak and M.Kabasakaloglu, *Applied Surface Science* 140,24 (1999).
- [48] J.Zhang, M.Klasky, B.C.Fetellier, *J.of nuclear materials* (2009) accepted 10 Nov. 2008.

- [49] R.Ambat and E.S.Dwarakadasa, *J.Applied electrochem.*, 24,911(1994).
- [50] R. T. Foley, T. H. Nguyen, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 129 (1982) 464.
- [51] Z. Szklarska-Smialowska, *Corros. Sci.*, 41 (1999) 1743.
- [52] F. Hunkeler, G. S. Frankel, H. Bohni, *Corrosion (NACE)*, 43 (1987) 189.
- [53] N. Sato, *Corros. Sci.*, 37 (1995) 1947.
- [54] C. M. A. Brett, I. A. R. Gomes, J. P. S. Martins, *Corros. Sci.*, 36 (1994) 915.
- [55] S. A. Rehim, H. H. Hassan, M. A. Amin, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 187 (2002) 279.
- [56] S. Zein El Abedin, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 31 (2001) 711.
- [57] P. M. Natishan, E. McCafferty, G. K. Hubler, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 135 (1988) 321.
- [58] C. M. A. Brett, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 20 (1990) 1000.
- [59] N. A. Ogurtsov, A. A. Pud, P. Kamarchik, G. S. Shapoval, *Synth. Met.*, 143 (2004)
- [60] I. B. Obot1, N. O. Obi-Egbedi, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 4 (2009) 1277.
- [61] A. Y. El-Etre, *Corros. Sci.*, 43 (2001) 1031.
- [62] S. B. Saidman, J. B. Bessone, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 521 (2002) 87.
- [63] V. Branzoi and M. V Popa, *Mater. Corros.*, 2000, **51**, 635.
- [64]Et-Sayed, Abdel Rahman, *Denki Kagaku Oyobi Kogyo Butsuri Kagaku*, 1998, **66**, 176.
- [65] F. M. Al-Kharafi, W. A. Badway, A.S. El-Azab, *Cur.Top. Electrochem.*, 1997, **5**, 131.
- [66] H. H. Uhlig, *Corrosion and Corrosion control '85*, London, Willey, 1967.
- [67] I. Lukovits, E. Kalman, F. Zucchi, *Corrosion* 57 (2001) 3.
- [68] I. Yamaguchi, T. Yamamoto, *React. Funct. Polymers* 61 (2004) 43.
- [69] D. R. Buckle *et al*, *J. Med. Chem.*, **29**, 2262,(1986).
- [70.]R. Alvarez *et al*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 37, 4185, (1994).
- [71]. J. S. Tullis *et al*, *Bioorg. & Med. Chem. Letts* , **13**, 1665(2003).
- [72]. L. L. Brockunier *et al*, *Bioorg. & Med. Chem. Letts* , **10**, 2111(2000).
- [73] Klingele M H, Moubaraki B, Murray K S and Brooker S 2005Chem. Eur. J. 11 692).
- [74] Bag S K, Chakraborty S B and Chaudhari S R 1993 J. Indian Chem.Soc. 70 24
- [75] . Ailor W H 1971 Handbook of corrosion testing and evaluation(New York: John Wiley and Sons)
- 76 McCafferty E, Pravadic V and Zettlemoyer A C 1999 Trans.Faraday Soc. 66 237
- 77 Talati J D and Modi R M 1975 Br. Corros. J. 10 103
- 78 Kelly.R.G, Scully J.R, Shoesmith D.W, Buchheit.R.G, *Electrochemical Techniques in Corrosion Science and Engineering*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York 2002 148